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Freddy: breaking record for tropical cyclone precipitation?

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E-mail: enrico.scoccimarro@cmcc.it**Keywords:** tropical cyclone, lifetime accumulated precipitation, historical trendSupplementary material for this article is available [online](#)Original content from
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Depending on the location on the Earth, the amount of precipitation associated with tropical cyclones (TCs) can reach 20% of the total yearly precipitation over land and up to 40% over some ocean regions. TC induced freshwater flooding has been suggested to be the largest threat to human lives due to TCs. Therefore, a reliable quantification of the precipitation amount associated with each past TC is important for a better definition of the TC fingerprint on the climate. The temporal and horizontal resolution of state-of-the-art observational datasets and atmospheric reanalysis gives the possibility to quantify precipitation associated with TCs globally following the observed TC tracks. In this work we compare the TC-related precipitation in various observational and reanalysis datasets. A particular focus is given to the record-breaking TC Freddy (Southern Indian Ocean, 2023). Here we show that the time-varying bias in TC associated precipitation, due to the positive trend in assimilated observations, makes it difficult to assess long-term trend investigation based on reanalysis. To this aim we need to build on state-of-the-art general circulation models, free to evolve under historical radiative forcing.

1. Introduction

Heavy precipitation and flooding associated with tropical cyclones (TCs) are responsible for a large number of fatalities and economic damage worldwide (Rappaport 2000, Mendelsohn *et al* 2012, Mazza and Chen 2023). A reliable quantification of the amount of water associated to TCs has a pivotal role to help stakeholders and policy makers to anticipate and prepare for this kind of events, leading to major impacts on society and ecosystems. TC intensity and size, together with translation speed, play a crucial role in determining the associated precipitation amount (Lavender and McBride 2021, Tu *et al* 2022). TC rain rates generally follow the Clausius–Clapeyron equation, thus a warmer environment leads to higher rain rates (Trenberth *et al* 2003, Scoccimarro *et al* 2014, Stansfield and Reed 2023). Another important aspect for the quantification of the total amount of TC precipitation reaching the surface of the planet is the TC lifetime (Larson *et al* 2005, Dare *et al* 2012, Scoccimarro *et al* 2021, Zhu and Qiring 2022). With this said, the lifetime accumulated rainfall (LAR), an

important parameter used to measure the total influence of individual TCs on large-scale water budgets, results primarily determined by TC duration, which accounts for around 70% of the variance (Lavender and McBride 2021).

Tropical cyclone Freddy formed to the northwest of Australia at the beginning of February 2023 and tracked west across the Indian Ocean, making several landfalls, lasting longer than five weeks, and bringing large flooding to parts of Madagascar, Malawi and Mozambique (figure 1). While Freddy broke the world meteorological organization's benchmark as the longest-lasting tropical cyclone on record, previously set in 1994 for a 31 day storm named John (East Pacific basin, 1994), we aim here to quantify the associated precipitation, to characterize such event within the global TC precipitation climatology, and to focus on the time the storm spent over land. To this aim we build on available precipitation observational datasets previously used for similar purposes (Pérez-Alarcón *et al* 2023) such as the multi-source weighted-ensemble precipitation (MSWEP, Beck *et al* 2019) and reanalysis products such as ERA5 (Rivoire

et al 2021) and MERRA2 (Gelaro *et al* 2017) to accumulate precipitation patterns associated to TCs as from international best track archive for climate stewardship (IBTrACS) (Knapp *et al* 2018) tracks from January 1983 to April 2023.

It is important to highlight that, despite the usage of reanalysis products is fundamental to assess TC precipitation in the context of climate variables in a dynamically consistent manner (Jones *et al* 2021), it is well known that reanalyses employ different precipitation parameterization and different horizontal and vertical resolutions, together with different data assimilation procedures, contributing to a large uncertainty associated to the simulated precipitation. In addition, it is also well known that a certain degree of uncertainty is present in TC associated precipitation as from different observational datasets (Yuan *et al* 2021).

The comparison of the results obtained based on the aforementioned datasets with the ones resulting from state-of-the-art general circulation models is then expected to shed light on the role of the time evolution of the weather satellite coverage—and thus of the relative observational data availability—in modulating the TC associated precipitation trend.

2. Data and methods

2.1. Rainfall data

Precipitation data were obtained from four global datasets: MSWEP observations, ERA5 and MERRA2 reanalyses, and various models from the HighResMIP suite. MSWEP, Beck *et al* 2019) is a multi-source dataset that retrieves precipitation estimates based on gauges, satellites and reanalysis (JRA55 and ERA-Interim, Beck *et al* 2019). MSWEP has high spatial resolution (0.1°), 3 hourly temporal resolution and global coverage. MSWEP data spans from 1979 to near real-time. This dataset is obtained weighting different satellite and reanalysis datasets based on their performance. The satellite datasets consistently perform better in the tropics while reanalysis datasets consistently perform better at mid- to high latitudes (Beck *et al* 2019).

ERA5 and MERRA2 are reanalysis products. ERA5 is produced by ECMWF, within the copernicus climate change service (C3S, Hersbach *et al* 2020). ERA5 horizontal resolution is 0.25° , the time resolution is hourly, the time period from 1940 to present. MERRA2 (Gelaro *et al* 2017) is produced by NASA's global modeling and assimilation office. MERRA2

horizontal resolution is 0.5° , the time resolution is hourly, the time period from 1983 to present.

Climate model output is obtained from coupled atmosphere-ocean HighResMIP simulations (Haarsma *et al* 2016). To ensure consistency of time periods with reanalysis/observation, we extended the model historical simulation (1950–2014) with the SSP5-8.5 simulation (2015–2022), assuming that the observed radiative forcing in the period 2015–2022 does not differ consistently from the SSP5-8.5 one: the effects of the RCP8.5 radiative forcing are minimal between 2015 and 2022 in the future simulations. We include in the analysis the four HighResMIP coupled models that better reproduce the observed global number of tropical cyclones (Roberts *et al* 2020): HadGEM3-GC31-HM, CNRM-CM6-1-HR, CMCC-CM2-VHR4, EC-Earth3P-HR. Due to data availability, model rainfall is downloaded and processed at the daily frequency.

2.2. Tropical cyclone data

Tropical cyclone trajectories and 10 min sustained wind data are obtained from the IBTrACS, version v04r00 (Knapp *et al* 2010, 2018), for the period 1983–2022. IBTrACS data are mostly available at 3-hourly resolution. The trajectories are interpolated on rainfall data time frequency: hourly for ERA5 and MERRA2, 3-hourly for MSWEP, to obtain the best approximation of the TC center position on the rainfall maps.

Only TCs that satisfied a set of conditions were considered. We followed Lavender and McBride (2021) for this step:

1. Any cyclone not classified as TS (tropical storm) or SS (subtropical storm) was removed from the analysis.
2. The TC must exist for at least 12 h to be included. The genesis point is taken to be the first position with 10 min sustained winds above 34 kt and the decay point the final 34 kt observation. This will include the full track of a particular TC even if it decays and re-intensifies during the lifetime of the storm. When 10 min sustained wind is available from multiple sources, the variable 'wmo_wind' is used.

Originally, the IBTrACS dataset contains 4330 storms for the period 1983–2022. After these 2 processing steps the number of events is reduced to 3397: 1713 for the period 1983–2002, 1684 for the period 2003–2022. The selection of the 1983–2022 period permits to have the first and second halves of the dataset to compare with each other. Only TC Freddy from the 2023 year is then added to the list of considered TCs.

TC Freddy (February 2023) trajectories and wind speed are retrieved from the regional and meso-scale meteorology branch of NOAA/NESDIS website (http://rammb-data.cira.colostate.edu/tc_realtime/).

For HighResMIP climate models we used the tropical cyclones trajectories calculated by Roberts *et al* (2020). These trajectories were obtained using the TRACK feature-tracking algorithm (Hodges *et al* 2017).

2.3. Methodology to accumulate TC associated precipitation

This work involves the calculation of spatial and temporal averaged rainfall associated with tropical cyclones. Given the center position of a TC, at a given timestep, we associate to the TC all the rainfall falling inside a radius of 500 km. This threshold is chosen following Lavender and McBride (2021). Rainfall data are obtained from gridded datasets, and the distance of a grid point from the TC center is calculated using the Haversine formula. When such distance results to be lower than the 500 km threshold, all the rainfall falling in the grid point is associated with the cyclone. Repeating this operation for each point along the TC trajectory, and summing all the values, we obtain the total (LAR_T) of the tropical cyclone. With a similar procedure we also obtain the time series of accumulated rainfall (no time average) and the composite of accumulated rainfall (no spatial average) of a given TC. Land (LAR_L) values are obtained by filtering rainfall values only over land grid points. The analysis of LAR_L is restricted to cyclones with LAR_L higher than 0.2 km^3 , using the MSWEP dataset. These criteria restrict the number of events to 1946 cyclones.

Composites of TC accumulated precipitation are constructed averaging the entire-track accumulated rainfall of all the cyclones in a given set, in terms of spatial distribution around the TC center. Composites of TC accumulated precipitation over land are calculated in the same way, except for the fact that rainfall values are masked over the ocean. To be consistent with the analysis of LAR_L bias, also for land composites we introduced a rainfall threshold: only cyclones that accumulate at least 0.2 km^3 of land precipitation for all three datasets (MSWEP, ERA5 and MERRA2) were considered. This lower bound on LAR_L allows a better comparison between different datasets and different periods excluding cyclones that release little amount or no rainfall over land.

The significance of temporal changes in composite maps between the two periods (1983–2002 and 2003–2022) is calculated using simple random sampling (number of samples = 1000) with replacement (simple bootstrap method). The method is applied independently for each grid point.

Recordmaps are a novel way to show how the historical record of rainfall accumulation around the TC

center are spatially distributed. These maps show the portion of the TC radial domain where individual TCs accumulated the highest amounts of precipitation along their trajectories, compared to the others.

3. Results and discussion

Freddy released a huge amount of water due to the long-lasting track (figure 1) along the entire path (figure 2, panels (a) and (b)), but also released a large fraction of water over land, (figure 2, panels (c) and (d)) mainly due to the recursive landfall. Based on MSWEP, ERA5 and MERRA2 reanalysis precipitation data, Freddy sets a new century-record of LAR considering the whole track (LAR_T, table S1). On the other hand, considering only the track over land (LAR_L), the Freddy record over the current century holds only according to ERA5 reanalysis (figure 2 and table S2), but not according to MSWEP and MERRA2. If we extend the analysis back, before 2000, Hurricane John is the tropical cyclone with the largest amount of associated precipitation in the MSWEP dataset, while in the two reanalysis products Freddy maintains the record (table S3) for LAR_T (not for LAR_L, table S4). On the other hand, it is important to note that in all the aforementioned datasets Freddy results as the TC making landfall, with the highest LAR_T since 1983.

Hereafter we extend the analysis to assess the performance of reanalyses in representing TC-associated precipitation, since reanalyses are the tool we use to associate large scale patterns to TC activity (Schenkel and Hart 2012, Murakami 2014, Wang *et al* 2014, Hodges *et al* 2017). Such effort supports the evaluation and quantification of the TC fingerprint on the climate system (Kawamura and Ogasawara 2006, Scoccimarro *et al* 2011, 2012, 2020), together with the definition of the precursors of TC activity, a fundamental step to extend our ability to forecast TC activity over different time horizons (Scoccimarro *et al* 2018).

In terms of average annual precipitation from all sources, state-of-the-art reanalysis products—such as ERA5—show a tendency to overestimate the water amount over wet regions (Lavers *et al* 2022), but tend to underestimate the most extreme rainfall amounts, particularly over the tropics (Lavender and McBride 2021). This tendency is less pronounced in ERA5 after 2009 when precipitation estimates from ground-based radar are incorporated (Hersbach *et al* 2020). Additionally, the volume of satellite data that is assimilated into ERA5 and MERRA2 more than doubled since 2000, especially the ones based on infrared and microwave instruments (Diniz and Todling 2020). This is made evident in figure 3 where the time evolution of the LAR_T bias, accumulated along the track is shown for ERA5 (figure 3 panel (a)) compared to MSWEP, and also confirmed based on MERRA2

reanalysis results (figure 3 panel (c)). A less pronounced trend is found in LAR_L (figures 3(b) and (e)), consistent with the disproportionately less pronounced increase in assimilated precipitation measurements over land compared to the increase over ocean areas due to increased satellite data availability toward the end of the period studied (Diniz and Todling 2020). A clear improvement is also evident in the correlation between the MSWEP and reanalyses' time series of accumulated precipitation (figure 3, panels c and f for ERA5 and MERRA2). The better agreement between reanalysis and MSWEP observations in 2003–2022 compared to 1983–2002 period is also highlighted in panels g and h of figure 3 for ERA5 and MERRA2 respectively: in both cases the correlation with observations is higher in 2003–2022 and also the spread of the different values of LAR_T is reduced in the same period.

Considering the whole Freddy TC track (figure 1) ERA5 overestimates Freddy precipitation with respect to MSWEP by 12% (627 km³ compared to the 559 km³ observed MSWEP value, table S1). Focusing on TC precipitation over land only, the overestimate increases up to 30% (175 km³ compared to the observed 135 km³, table S1). The greatest discrepancies between ERA5 and MSWEP in this case can be attributed to the more extended intense rainfall pattern far from the storm center (red to yellow pattern in figure 1 panels (b) and (c)). Similar biases, more pronounced over land (up to 49%), are found for MERRA2 reanalysis (tables S1 and S2). Because of these high rainfall amounts recorded in reanalyses, Freddy emerges as the new LAR_T record when compared to all past TCs back to 1983 (table S3). As anticipated, this result is not confirmed by observations: using MSWEP as the reference dataset the Freddy LAR_T is lower with respect to TC John, the longest-lasting tropical cyclone on record globally, until it was surpassed by Freddy (table S3). The underestimation of LAR_T associated to TC John in reanalysis compared to MSWEP is mainly due to the underestimation during the most intense phase of the TC (figure S1, panel (a)), while during TC Freddy the accumulation rainfall is more consistent among the datasets (figure S1, panel (b)). This is in agreement with the increased number of satellite data—also able to cover the open ocean—used by both reanalysis data assimilation systems during TC Freddy evolution (2023). Such a large amount of observational data was not available for assimilation during the lifetime of TC John in 1994 (Diniz and Todling 2020).

For a better evaluation of the reanalysis products in representing TC associated precipitation, figure 4 shows the portion of the TC radial domain where individual TCs emerged in terms of higher accumulated precipitation along the path, during the whole period considered (1983–2023). Notably, ERA5 (figure 4, panel (b)) and MERRA2 (figure 4, panel (c)) underrepresent the dominance of John in

most of the observed 0–200 km radius domain, showing a better agreement with observations (figure 4, panel (a)) in the band from 200 to 500 km from the storm center only. On the other hand, a better representation of radial contribution to maximum accumulated precipitation emerges when focusing on the last period only (2003 onward, figure S2) as expected due to the highest number of measurement data assimilated in this second period. The historical negative trend in TC associated precipitation, suggested by Lavender and McBride (2021) based on TRMM data (Huffman *et al* 2007), is also confirmed by the present analysis based on MSWEP observational data, as shown in figure 5 (panel (g)). While there is still an open debate on the topic of TC associated precipitation changes (Guzman and Jiang 2021, Tu *et al* 2021, Shearer *et al* 2022), the responsible mechanisms—also strongly dependent on the sample size, dataset chosen, and basin considered—are yet to be identified and is not the aim of the present work.

On the other hand, the result emerging from the present analysis is that care should be taken in using reanalysis products to determine the relative role of ambient large-scale conditions (e.g. vertical wind shear, maximum potential intensity), in determining TC associated precipitation trends (Lau and Zhou 2012). This is because during the current century the large increase in available data for assimilation into the reanalyses reduces the bias in TC precipitation estimates (figures 3 and 5; Diniz and Todling 2020, Hersbach *et al* 2020). The difference between the biases in accumulated TC precipitation recorded by ERA5 and MERRA2 in the first (1983–2002) and second (2003–2022) periods is larger than the observed epochal change (figures 5 and S3).

Given the contrasting result in the past trend of TC-associated precipitation between reanalysis and observational datasets, a further analysis of the multidecadal trend is performed using climate models. While reanalysis and observational trends can be

Figure 3. TC precipitation bias evolution. (a) Temporal evolution of the lifetime accumulated rainfall (LAR) bias in ERA5 compared to MSWEP, storm by storm (small dots) and averaged over five years (large dots) considering the whole TC track. (b) panel shows the same bias but considering the TC rainfall over land only. Units are [%]. (c) panel shows the temporal correlation between the timeseries of ERA5 and MSWEP TC precipitation considering the whole TC track, grouping TCs by 5 year sections. Vertical error bars represent \pm one standard deviation. Same for MERRA2 (panels (d)–(f)). Panel (g) (h) shows ERA5 (MERRA2) reanalysis LAR_T compared with MSWEP LAR_T. Blue and red dots refer to the period 1983–2002 and 2003–2022 respectively. Units are [km^3].

affected by the availability of satellite observations and the way those are assimilated in the final product, climate models are only driven by greenhouse gases concentration forcings, therefore they are not affected by spurious trends. As figure 6 shows, the difference in TC-associated precipitation between the two periods 1983–2002 and 2003–2022

is not significant as we would expect based on physical laws and such a short period. In fact, even if an increase in rainfall rates associated with TCs is an expected response to global warming—mainly due to increased evaporation from the ocean surface and increased moisture in the atmosphere—the expected signal would be one order of magnitude

Figure 6. CGCMs composites of TC accumulated precipitation. HighResMIP coupled global climate models composites of TC-accumulated precipitation in period 1983–2002 (a)–(d) and period 2003–2022 (e)–(h). (i)–(l) are temporal changes between the two periods, for the four models, respectively. In panels (i)–(l) stippling indicates regions with no significant change at 90% significance level, no stippling where the change is significant.

lower than the signal seen in ERA5 and MERRA2 (figures 5 and S3).

4. Conclusions

Our results show that care should be exercised when using MSWEP for trend analysis due to spurious temporal discontinuities that can occur mainly due to the introduction of the additional satellite data sources along the time series (Beck *et al* 2019). Even more caution must be taken in the usage of reanalysis products such as ERA5 and MERRA2 for trend analysis over long periods. This is especially true for the evaluation of local extreme conditions, such as the precipitation associated to TCs, when crossing the end of the past century. The ability to capture local patterns strongly depends on the spatio-temporal fidelity of the assimilated observed data, and the number of satellite information digested by the reanalysis increased substantially over the time period studied, even more so than the fraction of satellite information feeding MSWEP. On the other hand, when focusing on land only, a better agreement between MSWEP and reanalysis is found (figures S4 and S5 for ERA5 and MERRA2 respectively) even in the first

period (1984–2002) due to the already consistent coverage of observational data prior to the satellite era. Keeping in mind that the limitations and biases of the various datasets is valuable to those who might use these data for city planning, emergency management, and other non-meteorological tasks, our result suggests that estimates of TC-associated precipitation in the period before the 2000s should be treated with care, as they might be affected by non-stationarity in the amount and quality of assimilated precipitation data. This is confirmed by the absence of significant changes in historical climate model simulations' TC-associated precipitation between the two periods (1984–2002 and 2003–2022). Three out of four models show a moderate increase consistent with scaling relationships expected according to the Clausius-Clapeyron relationship (Pall *et al* 2007), far from what emerges looking at reanalysis products.

Focusing on the current century only, based on all the precipitation datasets investigated (MSWEP, ERA5 and MERRA2 reanalysis), Freddy holds the record for LAR from a TC along the entire track (LAR_T). Keeping in mind the huge discontinuity in satellite data from the beginning of the current century, going back to the 1983, Freddy remains the

LAR_T breaking record at least when considering TCs making landfall.

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available at the following URL/DOI: <https://gwadi.org/multi-source-weighted-ensemble-precipitation-mswep>.

Data and reanalysis availability

All data:

- MSWEP precipitation data: <https://gwadi.org/multi-source-weighted-ensemble-precipitation-mswep>
- ERA5 precipitation data: www.ecmwf.int/en/forecasts/datasets/reanalysis-datasets/era5
- Tropical Cyclone tracks and positions: www.ncdc.noaa.gov/ibtracs/

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Author contributions

E S designed and wrote the paper; P L performed the analysis; L C supported the analysis during the whole process and contributed to the writing of the paper.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

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